

**MODELING A DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL ECOSYSTEM IN HIGHER
PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION OF DESIGNERS**

**МОДЕЛИРОВАНИЕ ЦИФРОВОЙ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОЙ ЭКОСИСТЕМЫ В
ВЫСШЕМ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОМ ОБРАЗОВАНИИ ДИЗАЙНЕРОВ**

*Master's degree, lecturer, Aktobe Regional University
named after K.Zhubanov, Aktobe, Kazakhstan*

Akmaral Bolatovna Aimagambetova

*Master's degree, lecturer, Aktobe Regional University
named after K.Zhubanov, Aktobe, Kazakhstan*

Dariga Kairgalievna Salmaganbet

Abstract: *The article presents a model of a digital education ecosystem for training designers in higher education. Based on systematic analysis and pedagogical modeling methods, its main components and functions have been identified. It was determined that the use of digital platforms, virtual environments, and artificial intelligence tools serve to develop students' professional and digital competencies, as well as to improve the efficiency of the educational process.*

Аннотация. *В статье представлена модель цифровой образовательной экосистемы для подготовки дизайнеров в высшем образовании. На основе методов системного анализа и педагогического моделирования определены ее основные компоненты и функции. Установлено, что использование цифровых платформ, виртуальных сред и инструментов искусственного интеллекта способствует развитию профессиональных и цифровых компетенций обучающихся, а также повышению эффективности образовательного процесса.*

Keywords: *digital educational ecosystem, higher education, design, educational platforms, artificial intelligence, digital transformation.*

Ключевые слова: *цифровая образовательная экосистема, высшее образование, дизайн, образовательные платформы, искусственный интеллект, цифровая трансформация.*

Introduction. The digital transformation of society is changing the requirements for higher education, necessitating the creation of flexible digital learning environments that meet the needs of the digital economy and labor market. This challenge is particularly relevant for designer training, as professional activities increasingly rely on digital technologies, including computer-aided design, 3D modeling, virtual and augmented reality, and artificial intelligence. Therefore, educational programs must support the development of professional, digital and creative competencies. Modern higher education is

evolving toward digital educational ecosystems that integrate participants, technologies, digital resources and services into a unified educational space, ensuring personalization, flexibility and continuity of learning. However, despite the active introduction of digital technologies, designer education still faces problems such as fragmented digital resources, insufficient platform integration and limited interaction with professional communities.

The growing use of artificial intelligence in design further increases the need to modernize educational approaches and develop

competencies related to intelligent digital tools. At the same time, the Lifelong Learning concept requires educational ecosystems to support continuous professional development and cooperation with employers and creative industries. Despite significant research on educational digitalization, the theoretical and methodological foundations for designing digital educational ecosystems for designers remain insufficiently developed. This determines the purpose of the study: to develop and substantiate a structural-functional model of a digital educational ecosystem for higher professional education of designers. The scientific significance of the research lies in expanding theoretical understanding of digital educational ecosystems, while its practical significance is associated with the application of the proposed model in design-oriented higher education institutions.

Materials and methods of research. The study of the problem of modeling the digital educational ecosystem in higher professional education of designers is based on modern scientific concepts of digital transformation of education, the theory of educational ecosystems, the competence approach, pedagogical modeling and the principles of designing a digital educational environment. The methodological basis of the research is determined by the interdisciplinary nature of the problem under consideration, which is located at the intersection of pedagogy, digital technologies, design theory, educational management and information systems. In modern conditions of digitalization of society, education is considered not only as a process of knowledge transfer, but also as a dynamic system of interaction between subjects of educational activity, information resources, digital platforms and professional communities. This approach requires the use of ecosystem methodology, which makes it possible to analyze the educational environment as a complex of interrelated elements that ensure the achievement of educational results through networking and integration of various resources.

The theoretical and methodological basis of the research was formed by the provisions of

the competence approach, according to which the result of professional education is the formation of a set of universal, general professional and professional competencies of students. Competencies in the field of digital design, visual communication, creative thinking, project activity and the use of modern digital tools are of particular importance for the training of designers. The provisions of the systematic approach, which considers educational activity as an integral system consisting of interrelated components, are essential for the study. A systematic approach allows us to determine the structure of the digital educational ecosystem, establish functional links between its elements and identify mechanisms for ensuring the sustainable development of the educational environment. The ecosystem approach, which has become widespread in digital education research, plays an important role. Within the framework of this approach, the educational ecosystem is considered as an open self-developing system, including students, teachers, employers, digital platforms, educational resources and professional communities. The ecosystem approach provides an opportunity to design flexible educational structures that can adapt to the changing demands of the labor market and technological development. The research methodology is also based on the principles of digital pedagogy, which involve the use of digital technologies to organize the educational process, personalize learning and form a digital culture of students. Special attention is paid to the integration of artificial intelligence technologies, cloud services, virtual and augmented reality into the training of future designers.

The research is based on the hypothesis that the effectiveness of professional training of future designers will increase significantly if a digital educational ecosystem is developed and implemented that ensures the integration of educational resources, digital technologies, project activities and professional interaction in a single digital space.

It is assumed that the developed digital educational ecosystem will contribute to:

1. improving the quality of professional training of students;
2. development of digital competencies of future designers;
3. formation of project and research skills;
4. expanding the possibilities of personalizing training;
5. strengthening the interaction between the educational organization and the professional community;
6. to increase the level of graduates' readiness for professional activity in the digital economy.

The research materials were scientific publications by domestic and foreign authors devoted to the issues of digitalization of education, educational ecosystems, digital pedagogy, training of designers and the use of digital technologies in educational activities.

In the course of the research, the following were analyzed:

1. regulatory documents in the field of digital transformation of education;
2. Government programs for the development of education and science;
3. International recommendations on the digitalization of the educational process;
4. scientific articles indexed in Scopus, Web of Science, Springer, Elsevier, and ERIC databases;
5. Proceedings of international conferences on digital education and design;
6. educational programs of higher educational institutions that train designers;
7. digital educational platforms and services used in the professional training of creative specialists.

Special attention was paid to the analysis of modern digital educational platforms, including Learning Management Systems, cloud-based educational services, collaborative project platforms, virtual laboratories, and digital design tools. The empirical basis of the study was the results of an analysis of existing practices of digitalization of the educational process in higher education organizations that train specialists in the fields of design, architecture, digital art and creative industries. A set of complementary

research methods was used to achieve this goal and solve research problems. Theoretical methods. The main research method was the analysis of scientific literature, which made it possible to determine the current state of knowledge of the problem of digital educational ecosystems and identify the main trends in the development of digital education. The comparative analysis method was used to compare different models of digital educational environments and identify their advantages and limitations in the context of designer training. The method of systematization and generalization of scientific data was used to form the conceptual provisions of the study and identify the key components of the digital educational ecosystem. The method of pedagogical forecasting made it possible to identify promising areas for the development of the digital educational environment in the context of the introduction of artificial intelligence technologies and the digital transformation of the educational process.

The modeling method. The central place in the research is occupied by the method of pedagogical modeling, which is considered as a scientific tool for studying and designing complex educational systems.

Pedagogical modeling allowed:

1. determine the structure of the digital educational ecosystem;
2. establish functional links between its components;
3. to develop mechanisms for interaction of subjects of the educational process;
4. create a system of criteria for the effectiveness of the model.

The modeling process was carried out in several successive stages: the first stage was analytical. At this stage, the analysis of scientific literature, regulatory documents and existing digital educational solutions was carried out.

The second stage is conceptual. The theoretical foundations of the digital educational ecosystem were developed, the goals, objectives and principles of its functioning were determined.

The third stage is the design stage. A structural and functional model of the digital educational ecosystem was built.

The fourth stage is an evaluation stage. The performance indicators of the model and the possibility of its practical implementation were determined. The design of the digital educational ecosystem model was based on a number of interrelated principles. The principle of consistency. It provides for the consideration of the educational ecosystem as a single system, including interrelated educational, technological, organizational and communication components. The principle of openness. This means that the educational ecosystem can interact with external actors, including employers, professional communities, scientific organizations, and digital platforms.

The principle of adaptability. It assumes the ability of the educational system to adapt to changes in the educational needs of students and the requirements of the professional environment. The principle of personalization. It is focused on building individual educational trajectories, taking into account professional interests, level of training and educational needs of students. The principle of technological integration. It provides for the integration of various digital tools and services into a single educational space. The principle of practice orientation. It is aimed at ensuring a close connection between the educational process and the professional activities of designers through project work and interaction with employers.

To determine the effectiveness of the developed digital educational ecosystem, a system of evaluation criteria was formed. The cognitive criterion. It characterizes the level of professional knowledge and understanding of modern digital technologies in the field of design. The technological criterion. Reflects the level of proficiency in digital design, visualization, and modeling tools. The communication criterion. Determines the ability of students to interact effectively in a digital educational environment and professional communities. Design and creative criteria. It allows you to assess the level

of development of project thinking, creativity and the ability to solve professional problems using digital design tools. The reflexive-analytical criterion. It is associated with the ability of students to analyze the results of their own activities, use digital data for self-development and professional improvement. The reliability of the research results is ensured by the use of modern scientific approaches, the integrated application of complementary research methods, the analysis of a significant array of domestic and foreign scientific publications, as well as the logical consistency of the developed model of the digital educational ecosystem. The reliability of the results obtained is confirmed by the conformity of the theoretical provisions with modern trends in the development of digital education, the principles of pedagogical modeling and the requirements of professional training of designers in the context of digital transformation of society.

Analysis of domestic and foreign research. The issues of digital transformation of education and the formation of digital educational ecosystems are one of the most actively developing areas of modern pedagogical science. An analysis of domestic and foreign studies shows that in recent years there has been a transition from considering individual digital technologies to studying the educational environment as a complex ecosystem that ensures the interaction of participants in the educational process, digital platforms, information resources and the professional community.

The theoretical foundations of the ecosystem approach in digital education have been developed in the work of foreign researchers George Siemens and Stephen Downes, who developed the concept of connectives. According to their approach, learning is carried out through networking and the formation of connections between different sources of knowledge, and the educational environment is considered as a dynamic network of interconnected elements. These provisions became the methodological basis for the subsequent development of the concept of digital educational ecosystems. A

significant contribution to the study of the digital transformation of higher education was made by B. Bygstad, E. Ovrelid, S. Ludvigsen and M. Dahlen, who consider the digital educational environment as a space for integrating digital technologies and educational practices. The authors emphasize that the digital transformation of universities is associated not only with the introduction of technology, but also with a change in the roles of teachers and students, as well as with the formation of new models of educational interaction. In recent years, considerable attention has been paid by foreign researchers to the formation of digital educational ecosystems. In the works of Milena P. Rojas and Andrés Chiappe, the digital educational ecosystem is defined as a set of interconnected digital components that provide continuous educational experience and support for educational activities. The researchers note that the key characteristics of the educational ecosystem are resource integration, adaptability, openness, and personalization of learning. A separate area of research is related to the use of artificial intelligence technologies in education. In the works of M. Bond (Melissa Bond), H. Khosravi (Hassan Khosravi), M. de Laat (Maarten de Laat), N. Bergdahl (Nina Bergdahl) and J. The current trends in the development of artificial intelligence in higher education are considered by Siemens. The authors emphasize the need for an integrated approach to the implementation of intelligent technologies and focus on issues of educational analytics, personalization of learning and digital ethics. A significant contribution to the study of the influence of generative artificial intelligence on the educational process was made by T. Chiu (Thomas K. F. Chiu), F. Ouyang (Fan Ouyang), C. Weng (Xiaojing Weng) and their colleagues. The researchers note that generative artificial intelligence is capable of transforming approaches to learning, evaluating educational outcomes, and organizing students' independent work. At the same time, the authors emphasize the need to form new pedagogical strategies and improve the digital literacy of teachers and students. The issues of integrating artificial

intelligence into university activities are actively explored in foreign literature. Evangelos Katsamakos, Oleg Pavlov and Ryan Saklad consider the transformation of higher education institutions under the influence of artificial intelligence as a complex systemic process affecting the educational, research and management activities of universities. The authors conclude that it is necessary to form new management models for educational organizations in the context of digital transformation. Research in the field of training specialists in creative fields demonstrates the increasing role of digital technologies in the formation of professional competencies of designers. Foreign authors note that the introduction of technologies for three-dimensional modeling, virtual and augmented reality, digital visualization and generative design leads to a change in the content of design education and requires the development of new educational models.

In Russian pedagogical science, the problems of digitalization of education are studied in the works of E.S. Polat, V.P. Bepalko, A.A. Andreev, I.V. Robert, V.I. Zagvyazinsky, V.A. Slastenin and other scientists. Their works are devoted to the issues of informatization of education, distance learning, designing the educational environment and the formation of professional competencies of students. E.S. Polat has made a significant contribution to the development of the theory of distance education and pedagogical technologies of e-learning. Her research highlights the importance of organizing students' active cognitive activity through modern information and communication technologies. In the works of I.V. Robert, the methodological foundations of informatization of education are revealed and the pedagogical possibilities of digital technologies for improving the educational process are considered. The author notes that the digital educational environment should provide not only access to information, but also the development of students' intellectual potential. A.A. Andreev's research is devoted to the development of e-learning and distance learning,

the design of a digital educational environment and the organization of educational interaction in the context of digitalization of education. The author considers the digital educational environment as the most important element of the modern educational system. Of particular importance for this study are works devoted to the training of specialists in creative fields. The Russian scientific literature examines the issues of the formation of the design culture of designers, the development of artistic and creative abilities, the introduction of digital design technologies and the improvement of teaching methods of design disciplines. However, most of the research focuses on certain aspects of digital design and the use of specialized software, while the problem of forming an integrated digital educational ecosystem remains insufficiently developed. The analysis allows us to conclude that domestic and foreign researchers recognize the need to move to new models of organizing the educational process based on the principles of digital transformation, personalization of learning and networking. At the same time, a number of unresolved issues have been identified related to the development of a structural and functional model of the digital educational ecosystem for training future designers, the definition of mechanisms for integrating digital technologies and artificial intelligence into vocational education, as well as the creation of a system for evaluating the effectiveness of the educational ecosystem.

Results and discussion. As a result of the study, a structural and functional model of the digital educational ecosystem for higher professional education of designers was developed. The model is based on the principles of consistency, openness, adaptability, personalization and technological integration, ensuring interaction among all participants in a unified digital environment. The analysis showed that existing digital educational solutions are mainly focused on content delivery and educational management, while designer training requires an integrated environment supporting project thinking, creativity, professional communication and digital culture. Therefore, the

proposed ecosystem combines educational, technological, project-creative and analytical resources into a single structure.

The model includes five interconnected components: target, educational, technological, design-creative and analytical. The educational component integrates digital resources, online courses, virtual laboratories and distance learning systems, supporting accessibility, personalization and continuous updating of content. The technological component incorporates learning management systems, cloud services, 3D modeling tools, virtual and augmented reality technologies, and artificial intelligence tools, which expand educational opportunities and improve the quality of professional training.

The design-creative component reflects the specifics of design education through virtual studios, digital workshops, design laboratories, e-portfolios and collaborative platforms. These tools support project-based learning and the development of students' creative potential. The analytical component, based on Learning Analytics and artificial intelligence, enables monitoring of educational outcomes, analysis of student activity and the creation of personalized learning trajectories. The results indicate that the implementation of a digital educational ecosystem contributes to the development of digital competencies, personalized learning and stronger interaction between universities, employers and professional communities. The study also confirms the growing importance of artificial intelligence as a tool for supporting project activities, concept generation and educational analytics, while emphasizing the need to preserve the leading role of human creativity in the design process.

The effectiveness of the ecosystem depends not only on technological infrastructure but also on pedagogical design, teacher readiness and equal access to digital resources. The findings demonstrate that the proposed model has significant potential for modernizing design education and improving the quality of specialist training in accordance with the requirements of the digital economy and creative industries. The

scientific novelty of the study lies in clarifying the concept of a digital educational ecosystem for designer training, developing its structural-functional model, substantiating mechanisms of ecosystem functioning, identifying the role of artificial intelligence, and proposing criteria for assessing ecosystem effectiveness. The practical significance is associated with the application of the model in university digital environments and the modernization of educational programs in design-related fields. Conclusion. The digital transformation of higher education necessitates the development of new approaches to professional training, particularly in design education, where digital technologies, innovative design tools and artificial intelligence play an increasingly important role. The conducted research confirmed the relevance of creating a digital educational ecosystem that integrates educational resources, digital technologies, project activities and professional interaction into a unified educational environment.

A structural-functional model of a digital educational ecosystem for designer training was

developed based on systemic, competence-based and ecosystem approaches.

The model includes educational, technological, design-creative and analytical components that ensure the development of professional, digital and creative competencies, personalization of learning and effective interaction with the professional community. The findings demonstrate that the implementation of the proposed ecosystem contributes to improving the quality of designer training and supports the integration of artificial intelligence technologies into the educational process. The theoretical significance of the study lies in expanding the conceptual foundations of digital educational ecosystems, while its practical significance is associated with the application of the proposed model in higher education institutions. Further research should focus on experimental validation of the model and assessment of its effectiveness in developing designers' digital competencies.

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